

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

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METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *It is important that, there are different methods for teaching English. In teaching English, it is necessary to use and pay attention to new ways for developing students' speech. However, several classic schools are still trying to use old books and methods. At the same instant, they will be some problems, and they also do not satisfy their English level and the quality of the lessons. This article purposes to improve students' language ability and to discuss some interesting and useful methods.*

Key words: *method, teacher, game, English, school, student, learners, Foreign Language.*

Introduction

Learning a new language used to be just memorizing words and phrases, but that was a long time ago. Learning a new language used to be just about memorizing boring rules and being able to translate words. That was as good as it got. Many different ways to learn a new language have been around for a long time, but new and better ways to teach English only started in the XX century. Nowadays, everyone is studying a language from another country. As more people join, there are more ways to do things. However, each method has good and bad points.

Today, people criticize the old school ways even though they were effective and successful. The only thing to think about is how much we had to pay to get these results. Usually, people have to spend a lot of time reading, translating, and practicing new words and exercises in order to learn a language well. To switch things up, students could choose to write essays or do dictation exercises. In today's world, learning a foreign language is really important for job training. People first learn this knowledge in school, college, and high school. Later, they can learn more at training courses or by teaching themselves basic information to learn a new language.

Most people strongly believe that human communication is a complex process, though it is a vital part of their life. Furthermore, none can information explosion,

English has become this common language and so learning it has been essential. To master such a global language, learners have to master its main skills beginning with listening and ending with writing. Out of these skills, speaking might be the most difficult skill to master because speakers have to produce both grammatically and meaningfully correct utterances [Rao PS.,2019]. Moreover, the teaching methods, teachers often adopt, play a significant role in motivating learners to learn this foreign language, i.e English as most of them face anxiety and feel shy to speak

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in front of peers and others. Hence, adopted teaching methods and activities should minimize the challenges faced during the educational process while teaching speaking [Kaur D, Abdul Aziz A.,2020].

On the other part, learners' success in communication depends on how accurate and fluent they are when speaking. Their accuracy and fluency normally reflect the effect of the English courses they are usually subjected to [Sayin BA.,2015]. Consequently, teachers should always look for ways to help them improve their speaking performance [Ho P, Thien N, An N, Vy N.,2020]. Learning by doing or playing, provided by the use of games, is also regarded very important by many educationalists. It can help learners get over their boredom resulting from serious, strict, and monotonous study in classroom [Amrullah AZ.,2015]. Nowadays, electronic educational games can be and integrated in Different forms of electronic games can be used in a variety of ways to educational practice and the easiest way could be in using the game content as a multiple-choice test, where the game could be the learners' actual reward [Sung HY, Hwang GJ, Lin CJ, Hong TW.,2017].

Recent studies such as Ho, Thien, An, & Vy [Ho P, Thien N, An N, Vy N.,2020] believed that gaming in the classroom can have a great effect on training students on how to use the language because of its ability to encourage students to interact with each other, work together and become more creative in expressing their ideas. In addition, Meiningsih & Madya [Meiningsih FA, Madya S.,2021] showed that students' speaking skills improved after learning through the use of guessing games and the main sub-skills that improved significantly were pronunciation, vocabulary, and fluency. However, Grammar and comprehension were not improved significantly.

One more interesting factor that, encourages the use of educational games in classrooms is the fact that games themselves can be effective techniques in teaching any language not only the foreign one. They are attractive and meanwhile attract the attention of learners to use language in a funny way. They allow English as a Foreign Language learners the opportunity to orally express their opinions and to interact not only with their friends but also with their teachers [Rabbani N, Vianty M, Zuraida.,2016].

Motivation might be the most significant factor in helping English as a Foreign Language learners to speak courageously and confidently without stress and anxiety. Good motivation affects the learners' willingness to practice using English regularly. Creativity of English as a Foreign Language teachers to plan and develop more

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creative and innovative activities can also enhance learners' skills and mainly speaking [Syakur MR.,2020].

Conclusion

Games like Fruit Naming Game, Guessing Game, Match Words and Pictures Game, and a Sentence Forming Game are used to help EFL learners get better at using language. Most studies show that games can help students learn English in a different way. It can help them get better at the language. However, EFL language games should be used as planned activities for teaching. This study didn't solve EFL learners' language problems, but it showed that using games in the classroom can be a new way to teach language when technology isn't available.

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